

A comparative study of the metamorphosis of symbolic natural elements in Indian and Iranian mythology (case study: Classical elements)

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Abstract

Due to the long coexistence of these two peoples in the past, many similarities can be seen between the ancient mythological, ritual and religious beliefs of India and Iran. Mythology and literature serve as some of the most important vehicles for the expression of symbolic forms. So, if the symbols are related to the ancient mythology of a civilization, it will unconsciously affect people's psyche.

The culture of the two civilizations of Iran and India both have complex belief systems in which natural elements such as water, fire, soil and wind act as metaphors for creation, destruction and transformation. The **purpose** of this study is to investigate the metamorphosis of these symbolic elements in the mythology of both civilizations with a view to their religious and cultural themes. This research seeks to answer the **question** that what is the impact and impression of symbolic natural elements on the worldview and human beliefs of a society, and how does the separation of Aryan ethnic groups affect the transformation process of these symbolic elements?

The **results** of this research indicate that: according to the point that symbolization takes place with transformation in thinking. It can be said that the symbolic natural elements in the mythology of India and Iran are very similar before the separation of these two peoples due to the common ecosystem. But things like: the influence of the native culture of the conquered regions after the separation, the new environmental and atmospheric conditions, the passage of time and changes in religious beliefs, such as: the tendency to monotheism instead of polytheism and the continuation of the existence of other gods in the form of Iranian epic warriors is one of the inconsistencies in the mythology of these two cultures.

Keywords: myth, Indo-European mythology, Indo-Iranian mythology, symbolism, four elements, symbolic elements

Introduction

The world of mythology speaks of the beginning of man life and refers to a time when man sought to understand his surroundings with complete wonder. It has always been placed in front of the absolute, transcendental and superior force (sometimes it has included the manifestations of nature) and various names have been chosen for it. The primitive man has explained and interpreted everything that he could not understand from the point of view of logic, by means of his imagination and primitive thinking. Mythologies are the forerunners of sacred religions and have always been respected by humans, and in fact, they are models for human actions and character.

The life of the myth is as long as history, which is related to the human being, which has gained meaning and developed. The mythological traditions of Iran and India are full of symbolic natural elements that reflect the fundamental human experiences and universal values of mankind, and hence cause the connection of man with the universe and divinity.

This research first introduces the main concepts discussed and then metamorphoses and how the elements of nature evolve, which are symbolically present in the mythology of Iran and India; examines the similarities and differences between them and their symbolic meanings, transformations and their cultural significance and the influence of beliefs and culture on how they transform checks This research has a holistic approach and a case study on the four elements of the universe. It is hoped that in the future research, other elements of nature will be analyzed and investigated in a specialized and special way, so that the hidden angles will be revealed as much as possible.

Research method

This research is an analytical, qualitative and comparative study that compares the metamorphosis of the symbolic elements of nature by using the analytical descriptive method and using library resources.

The Myth

It is not possible to know the myth in a single definition with all its dimensions and completely to others. Because myth is a very complicated phenomenon and it can only be investigated with different approaches such as: historical, psychological, sociological or religious. On the surface, the myth has a seductive and attractive form that originates from the inner desire of man to hear the story. But in the innermost layers, it expresses what and how the phenomena of nature, the creation of the world and the events after that. Mythology is not a fictional story Rather, it is history. A false history and a real story that tells about real events due to its content (Shaygan, 1992: 105).

Humans have always interacted with nature since the beginning of time and were astonished to see its changes. Universe has challenged and forced him to think about what, why and how it is. In search of finding answers to questions and solving ambiguities, man sometimes gets stressed and bows down to some natural elements that he thinks have great power, to the extent that he considers them to be in the domain of gods. On the other hand, he considered some of these elements to be evil and destructive.

Mythology is considered as a part of the identity of a culture, in addition to that, they are considered important factors in the creation of early civilizations, fulfilling the spiritual and material needs of human beings. A myth is the result of human beliefs and thoughts, so by being manifested in a symbol, it affects the human spirit and soul more and more. This is how a person learns the way to live and how to give meaning to it. Mythological symbols bring people to religious beliefs and concepts and they appear in the form of different stories in human social life.

Myth is a sign of ancient people's life and is intertwined with all their rituals and beliefs. Myth is a sign of human experiences and embodies the spiritual values of a culture. Mythology implies the survival of a culture due to its inner beliefs. Therefore, in order to preserve the immortality of its culture, the society tries to preserve its own myths. Generally, myth has two purposes: It seeks to describe the nature of existence and how it is (such as creation and fertility myths) Or It seeks to educate the members of the society to work better and have a special culture and success by taking appropriate action and behavior (Rosenberg, 2001: 17). Myth has been an attempt to organize the world and give meaning to it. For this reason, it can be considered as the starting point of philosophy because man has been trying to put the unknown things in order, whether internal or external, to endure them.

The symbol

With the help of words, a person expresses a mental concept including: his thoughts or opinions in the form of speech or writing. Some words, in addition to their concrete, common and obvious meaning, have daily applications in human life. It can have an implied meaning that implies something else. These words are called symbols. Symbolism has a vast unconscious aspect that has never been precisely defined. In search of its meaning, man reaches ideas beyond the scope of normal reasoning. The subject is one of the reasons that shows why all religions use symbolic language (Jung, 1998, 17). The symbol may have an external meaning or, on the contrary, it may represent a completely esoteric concept. Therefore, the first impression does not necessarily mean a complete and superior interpretation. In dealing with the realities of his world, primitive man depicted his experiences with the help of symbolic meaning structure and gave meaning to his life. Therefore, today's man can understand the culture and thoughts of his ancestors through symbols.

Man is a social being and the presence of symbols in human life is necessary as a tool for social interaction. For a better interpretation of different cultures and ethnicities and a better understanding of ritual behaviors and ancient customs, At first it is necessary to gain sufficient

knowledge of various symbols in that culture. Otherwise, symbolic behaviors and mythological stories will be interpreted as children's stories with and without meaning. Investigating symbols in the context of a society's culture is very important because the culture of a nation is one of the basic pillars of that society and a huge part of society and its people's behavior is affected by culture. Group relations and social interaction are organized by society members only in the shadow of culture and cause social cohesion and integration (Fouladi. Hassanpour. 2014: 5). Culture also refers to the lifestyle of the members of a certain society, their habits and customs, along with the material goods they produce (Giddens, 2008: 36).

In the Larousse encyclopedia, considers culture as a collection of things that are related to the civilization of a specific group. This collection includes: sciences, beliefs, art, ethics, laws, customs and any other regulations and habits that man has acquired as a member of society (Rafi, 1994: 266).

Symbols are also one of the signs of culture and one of the most important elements of its existence. The symbol shows a concept other than its apparent meaning and is the result of a social agreement that is rooted in the traditions of its people and has been passed down from generation to generation throughout the ages. Because the hidden meaning in symbols is common among many cultures. It is possible to find cultural similarities of different societies through their study.

Despite the apparent simplicity and lack of science and technology, the ancient man, unlike the modern man, had a very high understanding of nature. The interaction of the two sides of man and nature has led to the formation of naturalist symbols in popular culture (Fouladi. Hassanpour. 2016: 141)

Migration of Aryans to Iran and India

Aryans living in Central Asia, who are called Indo-Europeans. Around two thousand years before Christ, a branch of them named Indo-Iranian migrated to the lands of Iran and India. Despite their separation in terms of place of residence, some cultural and racial commonalities were never separated between the two groups. This correlation is clearly seen especially in their language, mythology and rituals. Which is indeed a sign of their long coexistence in the past (Bahar, 1999: 18).

Nature was very precious according to the common ancestors of these two civilizations. As the beneficial manifestations of nature such as: sky, water, fire, thunder and rain had a sacred position in their opinion. Unhelpful effects such as: drought and lack of rain are considered among the demons. The Aryans imagined the land demons in the form of black clouds that have collected the waters of nature. They called the biggest cloud, which was actually their biggest enemy, Vritra (meaning: thief or concealer). On the other hand, rain clouds were sometimes compared to cows and sometimes to beautiful women who have children named lightning and carry holy water (Moein. 1992: 46-47).

Narrating the facts of ancient people's lives over time became symbolic elements and were further represented in legends and epic texts such as Shahnameh, Ramayana and Mahabharata. Because

the myths of different nations are connected with each other, especially the myths of Iran and India, which have a common ancestry. Although the Aryan peoples of India and Iran built the foundations of Aryan civilization and culture in different lands and separately from each other; However, maybe the racial and cultural commonalities between India and Iran were never separated (Campbell. 2010: 3). Their commonality is rooted in the collective unconscious of these two nations, which is related to their common homeland before the migration (Dadvar. 2015: 41). Among the commonalities of these two peoples, we can point out polytheism, making sacrifices to the gods and drinking an unknown herbal juice called Soma (Huma) in ritual ceremonies.

Similarity in the symbolic representation of the elements of nature in the two civilizations of India and Iran

The elements in nature are always related to each other. In the mythology of Iran and India, even though the elements of nature are used in a symbolic way, they are defined in a deep and multifaceted relationship with each other and in the form of important cultural and religious elements. Symbolic expression is very important in literature because: it creates a suitable platform for putting together conflicting ideas and different narratives. In addition, it makes difficult and complex concepts and ideas understandable to everyone.

According to the assumption of the existence of the dual nature of male and female, which exists more or less in the mythology of ancient civilizations, especially the myth of creation. By observing in Zarvanian documents, it appears that in order to create unity among the classical elements, water and earth are mentioned as feminine elements and fire and wind as masculine elements (Zinner, 1996: 122).

The water

Humans in early societies, because they were engaged in agriculture, had realized the vital role of water in the life and fertility of nature from the very beginning. Therefore, it is not surprising that the most prominent symbolization in the realm of mythology has taken the form of water. In both Iranian and Indian mythology, water represents life and purification. In Indian mythology, the Ganges is considered as a sacred River and it represents the flow of life and spirituality. In Iran, water is a symbol of purity and order of creation, similar to its role in the Avesta.

In the Vedas, water is introduced as the source of life and it is the first element created by the creator of the universe. In one of the poems of the Rigveda, it is mentioned that in the beginning there was neither existence nor nonexistence, nor night and day, nor death and life. Darkness lay in darkness. There were no obvious symptoms. There was water everywhere. Everywhere was covered by dark and unmarked waters. According to what was mentioned, water is the precursor and creation of everything (Bahar, 2008: 164).

In another part of the Rigveda, the existence is like a seed that floats on formless waters. According to Hindus, the four elements of water, fire, wind and earth are the primary elements that create universe. But water is considered the main substance and they believed that water has become the world with the power of time, desire, reason and heat (Qureshi, 2009: 89).

In Bundahisn It is mentioned that at first the sky was created in the shape of an egg. This belief originated at least from an Indo-European belief. Because in the oldest Indian mythology, it was believed that an egg was born from the nothingness that was existence itself. It stayed for a year. Then it was divided into two halves. One of the two halves was made of silver, which became the earth, and the other, which was made of gold, became the sky (R.P.V.U. vol 2:595). Therefore, water is the second material creation after the sky.

It is said about how water was created in Bundahisn: Then he created water from the gem of the sky to such an extent that [if] he puts it in his hand on the ground and it goes to his hands and feet, then the water will stand up to his stomach; With the help of that water, he created wind and rain, which are fog, rain clouds and snow (Bahar. 2008: 45). After creating material, Ahuramazda created Amshaspandan to maintain his creatures. Among them, Khordad accepted water self-care (Ibid: 73). After that, Ahuramazda also created goddesses and gods to maintain and help water.

The sanctity of water in the belief of Iranians is manifested in ceremonies and prayers related to the goddess of water Anahita. In Zoroastrianism, Iranians respect water and keep it clean. In the worldview of ancient Iranians, water before creation was also a symbol of stability and manifestation of the universe and the source and origin of all possibilities of existence, and it was the main source of growth and manifestation of growth and the source of life in all levels of existence (Abbasi et al. 2016: 120).

In Iran, Nahid has always been deeply respected and is considered the source of life, and has received deep and sincere gratitude (Hilenz. 2012: 41). This goddess with a very outstanding personality has an important place in ancient Iranian rituals and her praise dates back to the time before Zoroaster. He is the source of all fertility. It cleans the sperm of all men. She is the source of all fertility. She purifies the sperm of all men. She purifies the wombs of all females. She cleans the flow of milk in the breast of all mothers. While she is in her heavenly position, she is the source of the cosmic sea (ibid: 39). During pregnancy, women pray her for easy childbirth (Rezaei. 215: 2002). Hoshang the king of Pishdadiy dynasty and Jamshid, (the king of Fereydon's legend) have asked this god for help to reach the kingdom (Razi. 1967: 213).

In Indian mythology, Parjapati (The god of the father and the equivalent of Zarvan in Iranian mythology), the seed of the universe, began to worship himself in the beginning, and because water is necessary for worship; Water was found. Prajapati thought and rose from the beginning ocean and looked around and wept. The air was formed from a tear drop that fell down from his eyes, and from a drop that fell into the ocean, the earth and everything that looked upwards, the

sky was formed (Ivans, 2011: 51). It should be mentioned that the equivalent god of Khordā who is in charge of water protection in Iranian mythology, in Indian mythology is called Ashvin.

Sarasuti is the most efficient sedulous. She is the best mother and the best goddess. Her lovers and admirers wish for her to descend from the sky and sit next to their prayer table. She is the giver of wealth and the god of immortality. She gives energy and children and she is involved in childbirth. She ruthlessly destroys those who disobey the gods. She is one of those Gods who kill Vritra. In addition, she courageously supports his admirers and defeats their enemies (Bahar. 2002: 476).

Saraswati is the wife of Brahma, the creator of the world, and in Vedas, she is mentioned as the mother of the earth. Vedic poets write Vedic hymns beside this river, and as a result, this holy river became the master of poetry, literature, art, and music. Since Saraswati has a direct relationship with literature, she is considered the founder of the Sanskrit language. Sarasuti's status increases during the post-vedic period. During this period, while maintaining his connection with water, she becomes more connected with the manifestations of civilization and becomes the manifestation of literature, art and music. Perhaps this change of position is related and parallel with the intellectual and cultural development of Indian society. In Hinduism, that is, the later religious system of India, which is a development of the Vedic religion, Saraswati becomes the embodiment of deeper and more comprehensive themes. At this time, he is connected with intelligence, consciousness, cosmic knowledge, creativity, education, enlightenment, music, art and power. So Hindus worship Saraswati not only as the goddess of material knowledge but also as the goddess of divine knowledge (Zekrgo. 2014: 356).

Apam Napat is one of the gods of water. He is considered one of the gods who have similar characteristics in Iranian and Indian myths and his name is the same in both nations. Therefore, he should be considered as one of the gods related to the periods of common life of Iranian and Indian peoples (Rashad Mohasel. 2008: 12).

The fire

Another fundamental element in the creation of existence and the material world. Fire has always been considered very sacred and cherished by Iranians. According to Zoroastrians, it is so important that they consider it to be the manifestation of divine light and the son of Ahura Mazda. During the Indo-Iranian era, the worship of fire was at the center of the ritual and this ceremony was performed by the clergy class (Bahar, 1996. Vol. 2: 478). Lighting the fire during the ritual ceremony was due to its purity and sanctity and also to attract good forces and gods to drive away demons and demonic forces.

Considering the same descent of Iranians and Indians, there are significant similarities regarding the concept of fire and the beliefs of these two peoples. Therefore, the reflection of this similarity can undoubtedly be seen in the Avesta and the Vedas. In a part of the Avesta book, it is stated that

every creation was originally in the form of a drop of water, and in another part of the same book, it is stated that the origin of all creations was from water, except for the seeds of people and beneficial animals, which are from fire (Abbasi et al. 2016: 120).

In Zoroastrian religion, Ahura Mazda is the one who created the world. He created fire from infinite light, wind from fire, water from wind, earth from water and all the material existence of the earth. He first created the sky. He created water. He created the material earth. He created the fourth plant. Azar is also listed as one of the gods of Zoroastrians, who in confirmation of his great position called him the son of Ahuramazda and the rival of Ajidhak. (Zamiadisht. para. 46-50).

In Yasna 17, five types of fire are mentioned and praised them. These fires include: Barzi Suh, which is translated as great profit and means the fire of Bahram or the fire of the temple and the most important fire in the religion of the Mazdaists and Avesta (Yesna, 198). In Indian mythology, Bahram's equivalent is called Varathraghna. It means overcoming resistance and it is an attribute of the Indian god Indra (god of lightning and thunder) (Yarshatar. 1954: 433).

Among other gods, Agni is closest to him, who is the god of fire and equivalent to Azar in the Avesta. Repeating the names of Indra and Agni is mentioned as a compound word and this is completely natural. Because Indra is the god of lightning, and the cause of it is bright fire. Another god named Surya, which is equivalent to Hoor or god of sun (ibid: 436).

The earth

Among classical elements, the most stationary and motionless element is earth. Considering that the earth /soil in nature is a substrate for the growth of plants. In mythology, it is also mentioned as the primary material of human physical life and material life. In addition, it is considered a place for death and collapse and the end of life. The ceremony of burying the dead, which has been common among the oldest agricultural societies, refers to the fact that primitive man, looking at the growth of seeds from deep in the ground, He buried his dead with the hope of rebirth. Burying expensive objects and favorite items of the dead with them can be a strong reason for this.

Before a goddess is attributed to the earth or the earth is known as the lord of fertility. It has been directly as a great mother for the human kind. Because in the myths and beliefs of various nations, sometimes an orphaned child is left in nature, even though his death seems certain. But with the support of mother earth and cosmic elements, a destiny superior to others is established for him and he reaches the position of royalty or sainthood and is included in the group of mythological heroes. (Eliadeh. 1993: 245-246).

The first protagonist in the fertility myth of Indo-European mythology is called Damter. She is the goddess of the earth and her name is a modified form of an ancient two-part word meaning "mother of the earth" (Esmailpour, Noorani. 2007: 25). He taught humans agriculture and farming and changed their lifestyle from nomadic to sedentary through agriculture.

Earth/soil is a symbol of maintenance and fertility and according to the aforementioned texts, it as a feminine gender and the god associated with it is also the mother goddess and is embodied in a female form (Tresider. 1977:71). Ahuramazda created Sepandarmaz, another Amshaspandan, to protect the Earth. A goddess whose duty is to always keep the earth prosperous, fertile, pure and fertile (Afifi. 1995: 553). She is the goddess of earth and the daughter of Ahuramazda, the god of the sky. She is the helper of herds and the greener of pastures (Ismailpour. 21: 1998). Spandarmaz is used in Avesta and Pahlavi texts to mean land and is synonymous with soil and its fertility (Rastegar Fasai. 2009: 166). The god associated with the earth and its maintainer and helper is Zamiad. In different sections of the Avesta, he is mentioned as the god of the earth and soil, and he is worshiped in the Yasnas.

In the Vedas, there is a goddess called Prathoy, which means spacious. The goddess of the earth who patiently bears the mountains on her body and has kept the trees and plants in her sacred soil. Like a powerful mother, she humbly hugs her children when they die and as she had given them the ability before. After death, she accepts them again in his arms (Bahar. 1996: 447). It should be noted that due to the sanctity of soil among the Iranians and the fact that they considered the earth to be the gateway of the soul to the spiritual world; Zoroastrians did not bury the bodies of the dead (Mati Shirazi et al. 2022: 294).

The wind

It is a sign of nature's anger and shows the occurrence of chaos and disruption of the balance between the elements of nature. The god related to the wind called Vay or Vayu is one of the oldest gods among Indo-Europeans and despite its permanence and extent in the mythology of Iran and India, it is a mysterious and questionable being. He is the God who rules the space between heaven and earth.

In the Vedas, Vayu is a powerful deity and rules the air with his brother Indra. Although his real name is Vay or Vayu. But it is known by other names such as Prana which means breathing, Pavana which means cleansing, Gandhahedhah or fragrant, Satagah or always in motion and Vata which is another form of the word wind in Persian language (Jansen & Longman. 1993).

In Indian mythology, Vai is introduced as the creator of the island of Sri Lanka. A wise person named Narad asks him to attack a mountain named Meru. Vay attacks to Mount Meru, which is the axis connecting the earth to the sky. Garuda has spread his wings over the mountain to protect it. Vay destroys its peak and separates a part of it and throws it into the sea, which is the island of Sri Lanka (Vakili. 2012: 67).

In one of Avesta's Yasht named Ramyasht, Vay is fully praised. Many nicknames have been used to describe him, some of them are positive and some are negative. Some positive nicknames: strong, capable, strong, aggressive, conquering all, progressive, regressive, the bravest, hard, demon enemy, storm surge, finder of glory and negative nicknames such as: catcher of creations,

harmful, merciless, greedy is also known as a hunter and so deadly that it is impossible to escape from him. It is probably that it has become a symbol of natural disasters due to its fierceness and inescapability. In addition, the reason for this is that Vay is one of the most enduring Persian words (ibid: 68).

In the Persian language, people used Vay when facing an unpleasant situation to express regret or unhappiness. This may be to call the wind god. Because they considered the wind god to be the cause of random events and luck. Pronouncing the word Vay in the situation Unpleasant, it is common in Persian language until now. People use Vay in Persian language because of greed and need and loss of name and honor (Meibodi. 2003: 245).

It seems that the negative image of the wind god in Iranian mythology caused Zoroaster to ignore him. Despite this, the later Mughans placed him in the context of Zoroastrianism, like other gods such as Mehr and Bahram. But two different sides are intended for him: The good Vay and the bad Vay.

Astvihad is another epithet attributed to bad Vay, which is not mentioned in the old texts of Avesta and is discussed only in Vendidad. This word means "bone breaker", it refers to a terrible God who has deadly eyes and looking at them kills people. If it touches someone, he will sleep, and if his shadow falls on someone, he will suffer from severe fever (ibid: 75)

In Indian mythology, the benevolent and profitable side of the wind god belongs to Vay, and its angry and destructive side, which symbolizes the storm, belongs to Indra. Tvashtr is an Indian deities that helps these two appear on the wind. His female child, in connection with Vay, leads to birth and fertility and the creation of humans and solar gods, and his male child, who is a harmful dragon, is killed by Indra (Vakili. 2012: 72-73). This is despite the fact that the duality of the wind god was accepted in Iran. This issue is mentioned in Ramyasht.

Dissimilarities in the symbolic representation of the elements of nature in the two civilizations of India and Iran

The similarity in the representation of the symbolic elements of nature in the mythology of the two civilizations of India and Iran is probably due to the fact that they lived in the same place in the beginning and long ago. After the separation of the Aryan people and their settlement in two different places, the changes in the beliefs of the Iranian people due to the appearance of Zoroaster can be seen in the heterogeneity in the symbolic representation of the elements of nature between the two peoples of India and Iran. Because Zoroaster wanted to worship monotheism instead of polytheism. In Rigveda, as the oldest Iranian document, natural phenomena are personified and worshiped. Polytheism can be seen until the end of the Vedic period, but after the changes in belief, that is, the worship of a single god that overshadows other gods; For this reason, other previous gods have either been forgotten, or have descended from their position by

changing their form and name, and have continued their mythological life in the form of warriors. For example, we can mention the common deity of the people of India and Iran, Indra, who has descended from the status of a god in Iran and turned into a warrior named Rostam. Of course, some characteristics of Bahram are also close to Indra. But it is more likely that Rostam is a changed form of Indra.

On the other hand, it should be noted that symbolization takes place with the evolution of thinking and the importance of these symbols in mythology is directly related to a person's view of himself, the world, and his beliefs. Therefore, they may change in appearance during the period. But it should be kept in mind that their inner meaning should not be neglected.

Conclusion:

Exploring the mythological world and searching for concepts to decipher its symbols leads to discovering the hidden part of history related to man and his relationship with the world of the unknown and his justifications. Therefore, parts of the human psyche that have remained hidden until now are revealed.

When faced with natural phenomena, ancient people were forced to express helplessness and bow before them. Because sometimes natural phenomena are very powerful and appear in an uncontrollable way. During the long time, the perceptions of man from his surrounding environment have led to a kind of praise and then it has become a holy belief. Because they imagined some characteristics of natural phenomena outside the scope of materiality and gave them a supernatural and metaphysics aspect, which later transformed into independent gods.

Mythology requires imagination. In some traditional societies, the myth is still alive. Later, in epic stories, natural elements do not have a mere material presence. Rather, they have a soul and identity as they protect and secure the epic hero step by step against demonic elements in various stages of his journey. With the passage of time, the myths of India and Iran take on a more realistic form and gradually become part of the real existence of human daily life.

It can be said that the symbolism of classical elements in the mythology of India and Iran have many similarity. Similarities are due to their common beliefs, and the similarity in beliefs is due to the common primary ecosystem. Therefore, it can be said that these two civilizations have not adapted from each other. In addition to these similarities, there are also some differences that are the result of the influence of the native culture of the defeated regions after the Aryans split into two branches and settled in two different regions, namely India and Iran, and encountering a new ecology with natural phenomena and new environmental and atmospheric conditions. Another factor is the passage of time over many years, and another reason is religious tendencies, including the tendency to monotheism instead of polytheism from the time of Zoroastrian onwards in the land of Iran.

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